

Photon, Poynting Vector and Constant Velocity Electron Part II

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Einstein's energy-momentum equation $E_n^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)) allows for at least two very different solutions, one with $m_0=0$ and the other with $m_0>0$. In the first case, one may have a photon solution for which E and B are of the same magnitude for $c=1$ and E_n is proportional to $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 (E^2 + B^2) = \epsilon_0 E^2$ (where E is the electric fields and B the magnetic). For the case of $m_0>0$ (and a charged particle), the nonrelativistic kinetic energy is $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$. For the electromagnetic energy, $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 (E^2 + B^2)$ integrated over space, the Poynting vector $\frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ (integrated over space) multiplied by $v/2$ does not give the electromagnetic energy. I.e. the nonrelativistic scenario does not preserve $E_n = p^2/2m$.

In (1), it is argued that (for say a moving point particle), the "kinetic" energy is given by $\text{Energy}(\text{magnetic}) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 B^2$ (integrated over space) and in such a case the integrated Poynting vector multiplied by $v/2$ matches the magnetic energy. It may be noted, however, that the EM kinetic energy is $\frac{4}{3} U_0 v^2$ where U_0 is the $v=0$ electrostatic energy, so $\frac{4}{3} U_0$ is not exactly U_0 , the "rest" em energy.

In this note, we try to examine why this is the case. In particular, we argue that the two solutions of ((1)) are not simply based on zero or nonzero m_0 , but are linked to a no-source versus source picture. In other words, for $m_0=0$ there are no sources for E and B fields, while for $m_0>0$ there are. Furthermore, there is an asymmetry in the sources. E is in general dependent on a charge and B on a current i.e. charge times velocity. In nature, charge seems to be discrete while velocity (in a classical picture) may take on any value e.g. from 0 up. Furthermore, the low velocity expansion of $E_n = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2}$ suggest electromagnetic energy in the rest frame i.e. $\frac{1}{2} E(v=0)E(v=0)$ should appear in E_n and p in the moving charge (i.e. part of m_0). The magnetic field is proportional to v and $E(v=0)$ while $E(v) = E(v=0) + v \mathbf{F}(x,y,x)$ where F is a factor. Thus, it is the magnetic field which may give rise to a low v momentum $m_0 v$ in the Poynting vector i.e. $E(v=0)E(v=0) v$ while $E(v>0)$ cannot because it changes as v^2 . Furthermore, $KE = p^2/2m_0$ so it is magnetic energy which is thus associated with $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ because one wants m_0 to be linked to $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)$ for it to be consistent with m_0 . [Actually, using the magnetic energy yields an EM m_0 of $\frac{4}{3} U_0$ not U_0 , the electrostatic energy.]

This raises the question: How does one interpret $E_n = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 (E(v>0)E(v>0) + B(v>0)B(v>0))$? Both terms give contributions to order v^2 , but (1) argues that kinetic energy is only given by $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 B^2$. We try to consider these issues in this note.

Einstein's Energy-Momentum Equation

$E_n^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) ((1)) has at least two very different solutions, one for $m_0=0$ and one for $m_0>0$. In the case of $m_0>0$, it seems there is a rest frame for which the particle does not move. When the particle moves, $E_n = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2}$ which is a special form because expanding in low v yields $E_n = m_0 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$. One sees that m_0 appears in the v^2 term i.e. an "undeformed" rest m_0 . Furthermore $p = m_0 v$ (momentum) in this same limit. It is possible for energy to become

deformed when velocity is given to a particle at rest. Consider a charged particle at rest with $B=0$ and $E(v=0)$. The particle has a constant velocity which creates a magnetic field, but the electric field becomes distorted from a spherical scenario. The electric field goes as:

$$E(v>0) = E(v=0) + vvF(x,y,z) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one does not have a term linear in v and this “deformation” is not in keeping with the low v momentum $m_0 v$ where m_0 is linked to the Integral over space $.5\epsilon_0 (E(v=0)E(v=0))$. It is $pp/2m_0$ which should yield kinetic energy which is quadratic in v . The expansion of $.5\epsilon_0(E(v>0)E(v>0))$ yields a term proportional to vv , but this cannot be part of kinetic energy because it is not part of momentum. Thus, it seems that only magnetic energy can contribute to low v kinetic energy because $B(v>0) = E(v=0)(\text{perpendicular to } v) v$ as argued in (1). [Surprisingly, however, the magnetic energy gives $.5 (4/3)U_0 vv$ where U_0 is the rest electrostatic energy. Thus, when the non-EM parts of m_0 receive a velocity, it seems they must compensate.]

Source versus Non-Source

. We argue that the two solutions of Einstein’s energy-mass relation are not just related to rest mass, but to sources. For the case of $m_0=0$, one may have a photon, i.e. electromagnetic equations with no sources: $dB/dt = -\text{grad } x E$ and $dE/dt = \text{grad } x B$. E and B are on the same footing (there is a symmetry) because there are no sources breaking this symmetry in the EM equations. Thus, $E=B$ (for $c=1$). Then: $E_n = .5\epsilon_0(EE+BB) = \epsilon_0 EE$ and the Poynting vector $= 1/u_0 EE$ (with E and B perpendicular and perpendicular to v). Energy and momentum are the same.

For the case of sources, there is symmetry breaking because E and B are associated with different sources. E is associated with a charge distribution (say a point charge), but in nature charges are discrete, e.g. a proton or electron has a charge of ± 1 (although quarks may have fractional charges). The source associated with B is charge \times velocity. Velocity is continuous and may be 0 or very small. Thus, one may link the magnitude of B with its source and E with its source. If v is very small, B is also very small. When $v=0$, B vanishes. To have E vanish, the charge would have to vanish which does not happen.

This is important when considering the case of $p=m_0v$ and $E_n = .5m_0vv$. B cannot contribute to m_0 because for $v=0$ there is no B . Only $E(v=0)$ may contribute to m_0 . It is possible for $E(v>0)$ to be expanded as a power series in v , for low v . It is found, however, from Maxwell’s equations that $E(v>0) = E(v=0) + vv F(x,y,z)$ so there is no linear term to contribute to momentum.

This raises a question. If one expands electromagnetic energy:

$$E_n = .5\epsilon_0 [E(v>0)E(v>0) + B(v>0)B(v>0)] \quad \text{there are } vv \text{ contributions from both } EE \text{ and } BB, \text{ but}$$

the EE contributions are not part of $p=m_0v$ (because they are quadratic and the Poynting vector is $1/u_0 E \times B$). Thus, the vv term of $E(v>0)E(v>0)$ must represent a change in energy due to deformation which must somehow cancel with other changes in the overall “ m_0 ” structure as they attain a velocity, so as to preserve m_0v and $.5m_0vv$ in the low v expansion. We argue that

this is why it is only magnetic energy which yields kinetic energy in (1) and also accounts for momentum.

Thus, for a charged particle there is a complete symmetry breaking between E and B because the source for B is qv which is continuous and can be made as small as possible while the source for E i.e. q the charge, cannot.

Simply looking at the Poynting vector yields $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{E}_p(v=0)\mathbf{E}_p(v=0)$ (where \mathbf{E}_p is E perpendicular to \mathbf{v}) for the part parallel to \mathbf{v} , while magnetic energy is $.5\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)v$. Thus, without integrating over space one does not see the relationship $p = mv =$ magnetic energy, but in (1), full integrated expressions are provided and show this relationship. It is found, however, as already noted that $E_{\text{magnetic}} = .5 (4/3 U_0) v$ while U_0 is the electrostatic energy. Thus, the non-EM parts of m_0 need to compensate for v portion of $E(v>0)E(v>0)$ as well as for $4/3 U_0$ which should be U_0 . Otherwise p would not be $m_0 v$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Einstein energy-momentum ((1)) relationship allows for at least two solutions, one with $m_0=0$ and one with $m_0>0$. In the first case, $E=B$, $E_n=\epsilon_0 EE$ and $P=1/\mu_0 EE$ and in the second case, $E_n=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $p=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv} v$. If these are linked to energy density and the Poynting vector from Maxwell's equations, it appears that the two solutions represent source and no-source scenarios respectively. The no source scenario (in Maxwell's equations) means that E and B are on the same footing ($dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E$ and $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$) and so E may have the same magnitude as B. This means that $.5\epsilon_0(EE+BB)=\epsilon_0 EE$ and the Poynting vector is $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = 1/\mu_0 EE$ so energy and momentum are the same.

In the source scenario, there is symmetry breaking because the source of E is charge which is discrete and non-zero while the source for B is qv where v is continuous and may be very small. B, written as a series in v , contains a v term, while $E(v>0)$ only a vv term. Thus, $E(v>0)$ may not contribute to $p=mv$ (low velocity momentum). It is $pp/2m$ which contributes to kinetic energy. Thus, only B contributes to p and so it only contributes to the EM contribution to kinetic energy as shown in (1). It, however, does not contribute $.5 (m_0 EM) v$ with $m_0 EM = U_0$, the electrostatic energy, but rather $.5 (4/3 U_0)v$. Thus, it seems that the non-EM part of m_0 must compensate for this.

This begs the question: What does one do with the vv term in $.5\epsilon_0 E(v>0)E(v>0)$? It is not part of kinetic energy, but represents a vv change to energy. From ((1)) $E_n=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}=m_0 + .5m_0vv$, so a deformation in electric field energy (of the order vv) must be canceled by some other deformation in the overall m_0 (which contains pieces other than EM ones) in order that one have $p=mv$ and $KE = .5m_0vv$. Otherwise, there is an inconsistency between Einstein's energy-momentum relationship and Maxwell's equations in this respect. It may be noted that these arguments do not only hold for an electron, but for a macroscopic spherically distributed charge which satisfies Maxwell's laws and ((1)).

Given that the presence of a $.5\epsilon_0(E(v>0)E(v>0))$ deformation energy piece which should cancel with a term in m_0 (which becomes deformed as $v>0$) as well as $4/3 U_0$ and no U_0 appearing in magnetic energy, one cannot treat electromagnetic energy and momentum in a

moving charge as a four vector as already argued in (1). It is the total momentum and energy of the charged particle which forms a four vector.

References

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